

What, where, and how much? Downscaling spatial, sectoral, global economic activity

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Summary

The distribution of economic activity over space is a central question in economic geography, which can inform policies targeting sustainable development and regional economic growth, as well as assessing indirect losses from disruptions in the context of climate risk assessment. In this work, we develop a novel and flexible method applying Bayesian Hierarchical Modelling (BHM) to produce estimates of economic activity at high spatial and sectoral resolution, based on global, open data.

KEYWORDS: spatial economics, downscaling, bayesian modelling

The question of how economic activity in different sectors is distributed across space is central in economic geography (Peet 1969). In a globalised world, highly connected through supply chain networks which support trade in goods across many sectors of the economy, there is a need to understand the impacts of localised changes in, or disruption to, sectoral production around the world, in order to analyse systemic resilience and the potential for wide, indirect impacts (Levermann 2014).

Despite various survey and modelling efforts, globally consistent datasets describing economic activity, in terms of output (sectoral production) or gross value added, are available only at national or regional scales (World Bank 2024; Wenz et al. 2023), or at fine spatial resolution only as estimates of aggregate gross domestic product or productivity (Kummu et al. 2018), or for a few sub-sectors of the economy, for example in agriculture (Ru et al. 2023).

These limitations are particularly acute in developing and rapidly urbanizing regions, including low- and middle-income countries in Africa and Asia, where detailed data are often scarce despite these areas accounting for a growing share of global economic activity, infrastructure development and population growth. In the case of analysing disruption from extreme climate events, these also

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have a disproportionately greater impact on communities and the economy in developing countries (Hallegatte et al. 2017).

To address this gap and pave the way for a granular understanding of the spatial and sectoral distribution of economic activity around the globe, this work introduces a flexible method, relying on global, open data, which produces high resolution estimates of sectoral distribution and economic output in space.

1 Methods

The method involves three main steps:

- **Data Collection and Preprocessing:** transformation of incoming datasets to consistent file formats, spatial projection using the H3 grid index, providing standardised proxies, priors and constraints for the modelling.
- **Downscaling:** a Bayesian Hierarchical Model (BHM) integrates geospatial variables (e.g., population density, infrastructure distribution, night-time light emissions, and land use classifications) and coarse-resolution constraints on spatial, sectoral economic activity.
- **Validation:** datasets representing aggregations of spatial, sectoral activity, some with limited geographical coverage, are used to validate our downscaled economic distributions.

Data is projected onto the H3 grid¹. Raster data cell centroids are projected onto H3 at a resolution higher than the raster cell size, then a Voronoi tessellation fills any gaps in the H3 grid. Points are allocated directly to their nearest H3 cell. Polygons are allocated to all contained H3 cells. The resolution for projection of vector features is chosen to cover the equivalent of a small building block, ≈ 100 meters in diameter. Incoming POI labels are matched to ISIC activity categories at section level (UN 2008), providing the fine spatial resolution proxy for the location of individual sectors. For example, 'Overture: restaurant' \sim 'ISIC: Section I, Accommodation and food service activities'.

Inputs are taken from: multi-regional input-output tables for national, sectoral production (Lenzen et al. 2017a), non-residential built-up area (European Commission. Joint Research Centre. 2023), and points of interest and land use from Overture Maps² and OpenStreetMap (OpenStreetMap contributors 2017).

Validation datasets include: combined national/sub-national sectoral value added from the World Development Indicators (World Bank 2024), the CIA World Factbook³ and Wenz et al. (2023) and the US Bureau of Economic Analysis⁴ county-level economic activity.

The multi-faceted nature of the problem, which takes into account prior knowledge of the spatial locations, general laws of the distribution of economic output, and expert knowledge on certain sectors, naturally fits into a Bayesian framework. A BHM (Song et al. 2014) allows us to model

¹<https://h3geo.org/>

²<https://overturemaps.org/>

³<https://www.cia.gov/the-world-factbook/>

⁴<https://www.bea.gov/>

complex phenomena relying both on prior information, which can be obtained from heterogeneous sources, but also integrate a stochastic approach to parameter exploration. The modelling step is realised by running a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) process resulting in a posterior distribution. The output of this process incorporates our prior beliefs and adjusts them based on likelihoods given observed data.

The core of the model can be summarised as follows:

$$\mathbf{W} = \text{SkewNormal}(\mu, \kappa)$$

$$\mathbf{Y} = \text{LogNormal}(\mathbf{W} * \mathbf{X}, \sigma)$$

Where W is the matrix of econometric weights for which the mean (μ) and standard deviation (κ) are fixed using available information on the input proxy data and the constraints, X is a matrix of rescaled and normalised proxy variables, Y is a matrix containing output samples per sector per location, σ is the uncertainty, taken as a fixed fraction of the lognormal mean. This sampling is performed under the following constraints:

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{G}_\lambda, j \in \mathcal{S}_\zeta} \mathbf{Y}_{ij} = \mathcal{V}^{(\lambda\zeta)}$$

where \mathcal{G}_λ is a unit of the geographical constraint, \mathcal{S}_ζ is a unit of the sectoral constraint, and $\mathcal{V}^{(\lambda\zeta)}$ is the corresponding region and sector aggregated value at the resolution of the constraint, as illustrated in Figure 5 for both space and sectors.

2 Results

We model economic output (production) at an ISIC Section (letter level) sectoral resolution, and at a spatial resolution on a grid of hexagonal cells of diameter $\approx 10\text{km}$ down to $\approx 0.5\text{km}$. Figure 1, Figure 2 show an example output.

3 Validation and limitations

The downscaling problem is under-specified. We infer a metric of production at a combined sectoral and spatial resolution higher than any reported statistics or accounts with consistent and complete coverage. As the primary method for validation in various geographical contexts, we aggregate the modelled outputs by sector, space, or both, and compare them with known sources. As a secondary method, we propose to conduct spot-check comparisons of a subset of sectors with a high concentration of activity in well-reported sites, such as petrochemicals or steel manufacturing.

Figure 4a shows an example of the primary validation routine made with model output for Korea and Singapore compared with GDP (all-sector) data from Kummur et al. (2018) at $\approx 1\text{km}$ spatial

Figure 1: Global downscaled mining output. Mining areas were taken from Maus et al. (2020) and OpenStreetMap contributors (2017); Mining production values were aggregated from Lenzen et al. (2017b)

Figure 2: ISIC Section level economic activity output for Africa. Native resolution $\approx 3\text{km}$.

resolution. Some notable differences are attributed to the downscaling assumption, in our case relying on industrial points of interest, while Kummu et al. (2018) rely on high resolution population grids. As a result, the non-populated industrial clusters in the south west of Singapore receive significantly more output in our model. Further close-up inspection can be made on land use type figures, or with and underlaid satellite image for a close up visual inspection Figure 6.

Figure 3: Output per location and all sectors in USD (left) and log residual density difference with Kummu et al. (2018) (right).

4 Conclusions

In this work, we propose a novel and flexible method capable of producing estimates of economic activity at high spatial and sectoral resolution. This approach will accommodate improvements and adjustments as new datasets become available, or in application to more restricted geographical contexts with greater data availability, such as the UK.

Figure 4: Log scaled normalised residuals between Kummu et al. (2018) and the BHM outputs.

Figure 5: The two hierarchical representations for space and activity type

Figure 6: A close up inspection of output allocation allowing to observe the spatial distribution of the dominant sector in a cell (top row) and the underlying satellite view for the highest output location for a given sector (bottom row).

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Biographies

Ivann Schlosser is a Research Associate, working to combine and analyse global datasets of human economic activity, developing and publishing open source software for geospatial applications and modelling.

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Raghav Pant is a Senior Research Associate leading risk and resilience analysis research teams and specialising in evidence-based systems analysis across infrastructure sectors, including regional-scale multi-modal transport network risks and resilience to evaluate and prioritize climate adaptation investments.

Jim Hall FREng FRS is Professor of Climate and Environmental Risks, leading a research group which is at the forefront of risk analysis of climatic extremes and their impacts on infrastructure networks and economic systems, from local to global scales.

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⁵<https://devtracker.fcdo.gov.uk/programme/GB-GOV-1-300125/summary>

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